

Digital Twin technology for Catchment Restoration

Take a journey where the physical meets the digital world

[The Digital Twin](#)

[Big "River" Data](#)

[Catchment simulation](#)

[Decision-making](#)

[Engagement](#)

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Deliverable D1.3
Digital Twins of four
case-studies and "stories"

Imprint

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MERLIN Key messages

- 1. The Digital Twin case studies highlight four of MERLIN's projects and their use of Digital Twin technology.**
- 2. The StoryMap is designed for both the public and practitioners to learn about Digital Twins and their potential application in freshwater ecosystem restoration.**
- 3. The storyboard breaks down Digital Twins into four key components: Big Data, modelling, decision-making interfaces, and engagement.**
- 4. Each case study features a separate slide deck that showcases the restoration focus of the site along with one aspect of the Digital Twin technology.**
- 5. The portal allows users to learn about MERLIN, follow relevant links to dashboards, and interact with the site by sharing their thoughts on Digital Twins.**

MERLIN Executive Summary

This deliverable summarises the development of a StoryMap for Digital Twin case studies, including the process development, website architecture, and description of visuals and features. The StoryMap has been designed to allow different target audiences to learn through visuals and data-driven storytelling about how Digital Twins could be used in the future of freshwater restoration. The StoryMap showcases examples from four of the MERLIN case studies.

Created using the ArcGIS StoryMap cloud-based platform, the StoryMap is designed for a diverse audience, including students, researchers, citizen scientists, environmental practitioners, policymakers, and the general public. It has potential to impact public awareness, future research or policies and professional collaboration on technical solutions for restoration.

The StoryMap is a stand-alone tool that requires no ongoing maintenance. If integrated into the MERLIN project website, it could offer opportunities to assess engagement and inform future development.

Content

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1 Digital Twins StoryMap

This report describes the development and content of the Digital Twins case studies StoryMap. The use of Digital Twin technology for the restoration of freshwater ecosystems is a newly emerging and novel topic. The case studies in this StoryMap (Case 2, 11, 14, and 17) show the practical application of Digital Twin technology, including the collection of “Big” Catchment Data, implementation of data-driven modeling, evidence-informed decision-making and wider stakeholder engagement. A complete Digital Twin for individual catchments might not yet exist, but the StoryMap provides evidence of the benefits that could be soon realized from harnessing this technology within restoration initiatives.

The MERLIN Case-Study Portal is currently hosted on the ArcGIS Storymaps platform:

<https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/025b67bfceeb47068a4032e1cc8c4cd3>

This report documents the layout, content, and future use of the StoryMap as an interactive tool with which interested members of the public, scientific community and stakeholders can learn from.

1.1 StoryMap as the selected medium

StoryMaps were chosen as a visual and accessible way to share knowledge with different audiences, aligning well with the concept of Digital Twins, the focus of this StoryMap. StoryMaps are intuitive and support data-driven storytelling. In science, there is growing recognition that storytelling is a powerful tool for connecting with audiences and conveying information in a memorable way. This is not just relevant for students but also appropriate for policy and decision-makers who have limited time to learn about new technologies and need quick takeaway messages. By embedding data sources and references within the StoryMap, transparency is maintained, ensuring that users have access to more detailed information. The interactive features of StoryMaps also enhance learning by allowing users to explore and engage with the content directly.

StoryMaps also enable the integration of existing platforms (suitable for the different MERLIN case studies) and provide links to other relevant online resources. The ArcGIS platform is user-friendly, cloud-based, and allows for updates and collaboration across different contributors, further supporting its effectiveness as a tool for outreach.

1.2 Target audience & potential impact

Students:

- Students from both environmental science and technology fields can explore the platform. The StoryMap offers an accessible introduction to an emerging technology in environmental science, potentially encouraging interest in digital environmental management. It may also be used within academic programs to support learning about Digital Twins and ecosystem restoration.

Citizen scientists:

- Individuals or groups engaged in local or broader environmental issues can discover how citizen-generated data can inform technical solutions. The platform could further enable individuals and communities to contribute to environmental data collection and become more engaged in restoration efforts, promoting wider public participation in scientific activities.

Researchers and academics:

- Individuals in research can find this valuable introduction to Digital Twins and catchment restoration which might stimulate further interest. By showcasing practical applications, it may encourage new research collaborations, funding opportunities, and advancements in the development of Digital Twins for river and catchment ecosystems. Additionally, the StoryMap encourages discussion about the definition of Digital Twins in natural systems and explores potential next steps for broader application. Academics may also use this StoryMap for teaching or outreach purposes.

Environmental practitioners:

- Professionals in conservation, land management, and water quality monitoring can find examples from the MERLIN case studies that illustrate how Digital Twin technology enhances data collection and stakeholder engagement. As a group, practitioners stand to gain significantly by becoming more knowledgeable about this emerging advancement and understanding the foundational benefits of implementing Digital Twins.

Policymakers:

- By visualizing a complex topic, the StoryMap could support knowledge transfer on the topic and encourage the adoption of Digital Twin-related technologies in environmental policies in the future. This may, in turn, have a positive impact on the restoration of water bodies and water management practices.

Public:

- The StoryMap increases public awareness of digital technologies in environmental conservation and restoration. This may foster a greater understanding of their potential role in future initiatives and strengthen public support for environmental sustainability efforts.

1.3 Key features

The StoryMap incorporates several key features:

- Maps and map zooms
- Videos and GIFs
- Survey for users to ask questions about
- Embedded links to portals and websites
- Before and after slides
- Case study side decks

1.4 Development process

The process of creating the StoryMap began with an introductory discussion during the Vienna MERLIN meeting in 2023, with all contributors involved presenting a StoryMap demo on Digital Twins. Following that, we focused on assembling the case studies, which became the foundation for building the overall narrative. The final stage involved gathering feedback from each case study contributor through one-on-one meetings. Once we incorporated this feedback, all contributors had the opportunity to review the final version before completion.

2 StoryMap Architecture and Layout

2.1 StoryMap Structure

The main narrative of the StoryMap follows a vertical scrolling format, allowing users to scroll through the content. However, the case studies are presented as embedded side-sliding panels, offering a different interaction by sliding horizontally. The StoryMap is structured around the following architecture:

Title: Digital Twin technology for Catchment Restoration

- Freshwater restoration and Digital Twins (the ‘hook’)
- Digital Twin explanation:
 - Big Data
 - Catchment Simulation
 - Decision-making
 - Engagement
- Can Digital Twins work for natural systems?
- “Big” Catchment Data
 - MERLIN case study 11: Citizen science in the Emscher catchment
- Catchment simulation
 - MERLIN case study 17: A “digital observatory” in Scotland
- Decision-making
 - MERLIN case study 2: Justice for river pollution in Spain
- Engagement
 - MERLIN case study 14: Land-use change in the Oulujoki-Iijoki catchment
- Future Outlook
- Share with us

StoryMap webpage: <https://storymaps.arcgis.com/stories/025b67bfceeb47068a4032e1cc8c4cd3>

4. Engagement

Finally, Digital Twins are made for users. In fact, Digital Twins are essentially communication tools, and their success depends on whether users are able to learn from them. As replications of real-life systems, they offer interactive learning experiences for users to understand a system for themselves.

Figure 1 – Digital Twin case studies StoryMap: The 4 “ingredients” of a Digital Twin.

Figure 2 - Digital Twin case studies StoryMap: GIF showing layers of data that contribute to a Digital Twin.

Share with us

Tell us about your own experience or thoughts on the future of Digital Twins for rivers.

- Do you think Digital Twins can help river restoration in ways in which we have not covered?
- Do you have a River Digital Twin project that you can share?

Tell us about your own experience with digital twins for rivers.

Share your own experience and help us learn what is happening for digital twins.

1000

Submit

Figure 3 - Digital Twin case studies StoryMap: Survey portal for users to interact and provide their own thoughts.

2.2 Case Study Descriptions

Four of the MERLIN case studies are showcased within the StoryMap. Each case study is used as an example of an element of Digital Twin technology. Below is a description of each case study:

- MERLIN case study 11: Citizen science in the Emscher catchment – Showcasing the CrowdWaterApp for collecting citizen science data to feed into future models.
- MERLIN case study 17: A “digital observatory” in Scotland – A combination of process-informed data driven modelling is used to deliver near real-time information on peatland through an online portal.
- MERLIN case study 2: Justice for river pollution in Spain – A story demonstrating how automated high-resolution water quality monitoring can enable accountability for river pollution events.
- MERLIN case study 14: Land-use change in the Oulujoki-Iijoki catchment – Highlights a complex stakeholder situation where Digital Twins can act as a powerful intuitive communication tool.

Figure 4 - Digital Twin case studies StoryMap: Citizen Science in the Emscher Catchment

Figure 5 - Digital Twin case studies StoryMap: Embedded CrowData map.

Figure 6 - Digital Twin case studies StoryMap: Digital Observatory in Scotland.

Figure 7 - Digital Twin case studies StoryMap: Justice for river pollution in Spain.

Figure 8 - Digital Twin case studies StoryMap: Land-use change in the Oulujoki-Iijoki catchment.

3 Outlook

3.1 Future integration and sustainability

The Digital Twins StoryMap is currently a stand-alone tool that does not require regular maintenance or updates. It is hosted at the University of Stirling's ArcGIS platform and is accessible via a public link. A more long-term solution will be to integrate the StoryMap into the MERLIN project website. Possible options include embedding it within the Academy's Knowledge Centre or creating a dedicated section under the Outcomes area, such as a new StoryMap section. Should it be included in one of these more public locations, it would be helpful to conduct a review of how much traffic the platform receives to learn for further work or to expand the platform further.

3.2 Opportunities for future development

The StoryMap, through its interactive elements, has the potential to generate useful insights from user data that could contribute to learning more about how Digital Twin technology is, or can be, applied in natural systems. There is also scope for future development of the StoryMap, should there be interest. This could include adding new case studies as projects progress, incorporating additional interactive features such as discussion forums, and updating content to reflect advancements in Digital Twin technology. Ongoing promotion and visibility could help ensure that the StoryMap remains a useful resource for both public outreach and professional collaboration, supporting broader awareness of Digital Twin applications in environmental management.

